

STAKEHOLDERS

- Drinking Water Board
- Water utilities
- Irrigation consortium for agriculture
- Veneto region
- Local municipalities
- Parco Fiume Brenta
- Environmental association
- Citizens
- Farmers

CHALLENGES

Water withdrawals:

- Implying new **constraints** in the agriculture sector, the primary economic activity in the area
- Provoking direct **impacts for Natura 2000** (protected areas) ecosystems, by lowering the water table level

AMBITION

- Promote an integrated governance of water and biodiversity through a participatory and innovative **consultation management Committee**
- **Apply the Environmental and Resource Costs (ERCs) in the drinking water tariff** and explore the possibility to apply the polluter/user-pays principle also in other water sectors (e.g., agriculture)
- Develop/improve a **smartphone app** for households to create awareness raising, water saving behaviors

INN WATER PARTNERS

A **consortium** gathering 13 organisations (Research and Technology Organisations, SMEs, end users, associations with EU and international coverages).

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 @InnWater

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INN WATER

Promoting
social innovation
to renew
multi-level and cross-sector
water governance

Pilot Site #2

MIDDLE BRENTA BASIN
Italy

Led by

E T I F O R
valuing nature

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MIDDLE BRENTA BASIN

The pilot site coincides with the Natura 2000 Site “Grave e Zone Umide del Brenta”, located along the middle part of the Brenta River in the Veneto Region, North-Eastern Italy. The site is one of the most important sources at the regional level.

METHOD

1. Set the composition of pilot site community
2. Assess the current water governance situation
3. Set objectives and planning
4. Test and implement schemes and tools
5. Feedback and assessment

5 PILOT SITES

Implementing different types of governance mechanisms and covering different **water challenges**, test and co-develop the tools and methods.

INN WATER
Pilot Site Community

France, Réunion Island - **Economic focus**

Italy, Middle Brenta Basin - **Ecosystem services & Drinking water sector**

Spain, Figueres - **Water scarcity**

United Kingdom, West Country - **Water quality**

Hungary, Middle Tisza - **Water allocation**

